

Psychosis as Metaphor for Disillusionment and Bad Governance: A Study of Biyi Bandele-Thomas's *The Sympathetic Undertakers and Other Dreams*

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Abstract

Discourse on mental health has increasingly become central in contemporary literary studies, particularly in analysing the psychological consequences of societal dysfunction. This paper employs trauma theory to examine how Biyi Bandele-Thomas's *The Sympathetic Undertaker and Other Dreams* explores psychosis as metaphor for disillusionment and psychological distress caused by bad governance. The paper also argues that leaders who perpetrate bad governance and cause hardship, such as systemic failures in leadership, corruption and institutional decay, exhibit signs of psychological instability, including traits associated with dementia. Through Rayo, whose descent into instability mirrors societal collapse, Bandele-Thomas captures the fractured national psyche struggling with economic inequality and political oppression. Rayo's hallucinations and erratic behaviour symbolize the trauma and alienation experienced by marginalized individuals. Furthermore, the novel exposes how derelict healthcare and educational systems exacerbate psychological suffering. The paper concludes that Bandele-Thomas employs dystopian and scatological imagery to reveal the moral and psychological decay caused by societal neglect, urging a re-examination of governance and its impact on collective well-being.

Keywords: psychosis, schizophrenia, disillusionment, bad governance, mental health, Biyi Bandele-Thomas, trauma, Nigerian Politics.

Introduction

Biyi Bandele-Thomas is a writer whose novels are committed to portraying issues of mental health, driven by his concern for the stability of the human psyche. Bandele-Thomas' characters in *The Man Who Came in From the Back of Beyond* and *The Sympathetic Undertaker and Other Dreams* are afflicted with various forms of psychological trauma. Literature has long portrayed mental illness to reflect and showcase societal attitudes. Studies have shown that the representation of mental illness in contemporary literature tend to present characters with psychological disorders in a more detailed and empathetic manner. Literature as a whole is deeply committed to exploring and discussing the complex nature of human conditions within the backdrop of socio-political realities. Mental health and mental illness as themes in both medical humanities and literature are classified as literature and psychiatry, a subfield of Literature and Medicine. In the 19th century, the field of psychiatry began to formalize, with physicians like Philippe Pinel and Emil Kraepelin classifying mental disorders. Concurrently, literary works by authors such as Fyodor Dostoevsky and Charlotte Brontë explored the human psyche, presenting characters grappling with mental illness. These narratives provide understanding on the subjective experiences of mental disorders to

complement the clinical approaches of the time. Early American psychiatrists often incorporated poetic excerpts from English authors like Shakespeare, Byron and Scott, as well as writings from asylum residents, highlighting the close relationship between literary expression and psychiatric thought during this period. This cross-pollination between literature and psychiatry has continued to evolve, with contemporary works further examining and challenging our understanding of mental health (Jones 359–361).

Mental health is characterized by a person's emotional, psychological and social well-being. It affects how individuals think, feel and behave, influencing how they handle stress, relate to others and make decisions. There are various factors typifying mental health; they include biological influences like genetics and brain chemistry, psychological factors like trauma or emotional experiences, and social factors such as relationships, culture and economic conditions. Disorders like anxiety, depression, psychosis and schizophrenia emerge when imbalances occur in these areas, significantly affecting a person's daily life. In this article, our attention is on psychosis and schizophrenia which are literarily termed as factors that can make an individual to exhibit traits that are antithetical to good judgement.

Psychosis is not a mental illness in itself but rather a symptom or a group of symptoms that can occur in various mental health disorders. It is often seen as a mental state in which an individual loses touch with reality. This can manifest through hallucinations (sensory experiences without an external stimulus, such as hearing voices) and delusions (strongly held false beliefs, like paranoia or grandiosity). Psychosis can occur in various conditions, including schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and severe depression, or as a result of substance abuse or neurological disorders. It is often episodic, with periods of lucidity between episodes. Schizophrenia, on the other hand, is a chronic psychiatric disorder characterized by persistent psychotic symptoms along with cognitive and emotional impairments. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) identifies key symptoms such as delusions, hallucinations, disorganized speech, disorganized or catatonic behaviour, and negative symptoms (e.g., emotional flatness, reduced motivation). The onset of schizophrenia typically occurs in late adolescence or early adulthood and requires long-term management. Both involve significant disruptions to cognition, emotions and behaviour. In literature and popular culture, psychosis and schizophrenia are often employed as metaphors for fragmentation, alienation and chaos, reflecting both personal struggles, political and societal dysfunction.

These Mental health conditions marked by disordered thinking and perceptions provide fertile ground for exploring the human and societal dysfunction. In *Madness and Civilization*, Michel Foucault argues that mental illness has historically been framed as a metaphor for societal fears and deviations from norms. He suggests that depictions of madness in literature often reveal hidden anxieties about freedom, order and rationality (87). Also, R.D. Laing, in *The Divided Self: An Existential Study in Sanity and Madness*, describes schizophrenia as a state of existential alienation. He argues that its portrayal in literature symbolizes a fractured self, mirroring societal disconnection (45–46). This perspective suggests that characters experiencing schizophrenia in literary works are often emblematic of societal ruptures, embodying the tensions between individual identity and external reality. However, Elaine

Showalter posits that such depictions often mirror societal fears and misunderstandings about mental illness, reinforcing the idea of the "madman" as an outsider or threat (102). According to Sigmund Freud, "literature serves as a window into the unconscious mind, revealing repressed desires and conflicts" (152). This shows the parallels between the imaginative processes of writers and the fantasies of daydreamers, which suggest that authors often channel their own suppressed wishes into their narratives to allow readers to vicariously experience these hidden desires. However, writers do not only represent this, but also to a large extent, depict the struggles of characters with mental health issues, thereby providing a mirror for readers to see their own experiences reflected. In young adult literature, characters grappling with mental health conditions may provide readers a window into these experiences; thereby offering some forms of relief; as such literary works not only validate the experiences of individuals with mental health conditions but also contribute to reducing stigma by fostering empathy and understanding (Turner 14).

This advances discussion in both clinical and non-clinical settings on the therapeutic potential of literature known as bibliotherapy. According to Arleen Hynes, a pioneer in bibliotherapy, literature can serve as a tool for self-discovery and emotional healing by allowing readers to identify with characters and situations that resonate with their own experiences (45). This process of identification can help individuals gain insight into their own mental health challenges and develop coping strategies. For example, poetry therapy has been shown to be particularly effective in helping individuals express emotions that are difficult to articulate (Mazza 89).

This essay is hinged on trauma theory to depict psychological suffering, historical violence oppression, systemic failures and social disillusionment. Trauma theory in literary studies is heavily influenced by Sigmund Freud's early work on the unconscious effects of traumatic experiences. Freud in *Beyond the Pleasure Principle* argues that trauma disrupts the psyche, often resulting in repetitive and involuntary recollections of the distressing event (7–9). His concept of the "compulsion to repeat" suggests that traumatized victims relive their past experiences in various forms, which align with the fragmented, hallucinatory and psychotic episodes depicted in many postcolonial and political novels.

Building on Freud's perception, Cathy Caruth in *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History*, explains that trauma is not fully comprehended at the time of its occurrence but returns in haunting and belated ways (4). This notion is particularly germane in narratives that reflect political instability, war and systemic oppression, where characters exhibit signs of unresolved trauma through disoriented perceptions of reality. Caruth's argument supports the interpretation of psychosis in *The Sympathetic Undertakers and Other Dreams* as manifestations of the subconscious distress of individuals living under oppressive regimes.

Dominick LaCapra, in *Writing History, Writing Trauma*, distinguishes between "acting out" and "working through" trauma (142). He argues that victims of collective trauma, such as those in postcolonial and politically unstable states, often remain trapped in cycles of acting out traumatic memories, unable to process and integrate their experiences into a coherent narrative. This concept applies to the characters in Bandele-Thomas's novel, where the protagonist,

Rayo, exhibits signs of dissociation and delusional thinking, symbolizing the collective psychosis of a society unable to escape the burdens of bad governance.

There is a relationship between trauma, mental illness and political disillusionment. Kali Tal, in *Worlds of Hurt: Reading the Literatures of Trauma*, suggests that literature depicting trauma not only documents personal suffering but also critiques political and social institutions responsible for generating such distress (21). Similarly, Stef Craps in *Postcolonial Witnessing: Trauma Out of Bounds*, expands trauma theory to postcolonial studies, arguing that the Western-centric model of trauma must be reconfigured to accommodate the historical and systemic violence suffered by marginalized populations (6). This assertion supports an analysis of *The Sympathetic Undertakers and Other Dreams* as a postcolonial trauma narrative that portrays the Nigerian socio-political landscape as a site of both personal and collective mental fragmentation.

Textual Analysis of Psychosis as Metaphor in *The Sympathetic Undertakers and Other Dreams*

In *The Sympathetic Undertaker and other Dreams*, Bandele-Thomas depicts a vivid picture of a society riddled with social anomalies and psychological distress to weave stories that reflect the intersection of mental health, societal decay and individual vulnerability. Bandele-Thomas utilizes the fragmented experiences of his characters, particularly Rayo, to reflect the fractured psyche of the nation. The author tells the story of Rayo who is reported to have gone completely naked in the market. Rayo's life is marked by eccentric behaviour, activism, and a descent into psychological turmoil. This is the state of an average Nigerian in the midst of the harsh economy, who is one way or another naked, either due to the deplorable socio-political system that makes servitude of him or the religious inclination that has psychologically dehydrated him of sound judgment and perception of life.

Rayo's descent into madness is not merely personal but emblematic of a society in turmoil, one where the individual's potential is stifled by systemic failures. For instance, Rayo's early brilliance is evident in his sharp intellect as a child. When he questions Dr. Dakwa about a "painless circumcision" and demonstrates his familiarity with a thesaurus, the doctor exclaims: "This gentleman here is a genius. Hold your head high in pride" (15). However, the same society that acknowledges his intelligence also undermines his potential, leading to his eventual downfall.

Rayo's youthful audacity and activism manifest in his defiance to authority and attempts to challenge societal injustices. His confrontation with Senior Toshiba, a school bully, is both symbolic and literal. By sedating Toshiba and orchestrating his public humiliation, Rayo temporarily disrupts the cycle of oppression. Yet, his boldness often attracts punitive consequences, as seen when he protests against the school's outdated sanitation system on behalf of Baba Ayafa, the night soil man. The bewilderment of the principal at Rayo's boldness leads him to discipline Rayo. In a vengeful act, Rayo secretly pushes a bundle of broom into the principal's anus while he is using the toilet. Although the principal eventually regains consciousness in the hospital, the incident earns Rayo a form of publicity through the media, as he is portrayed as an activist advocating for the rights of the night soil man, Baba Ayafa.

Rayo's suspension serves as a condemnation of hooliganism, regardless of how genuine the cause may be. Meanwhile, Baba Ayafa is overjoyed at his retirement, marking a bittersweet outcome to the events. Obviously, someone in his or her right mind would not push a broomstick into another person's anus; this act is an evidence of an individual with dementia or a bizarre thought process.

Essentially, at the University of Ife, his act of heroism is also displayed by his well-organized students' revolt at the strike action embarked upon by the lecturers. These protests critique the failures of governance and resonate with the depiction of societal disillusionment. Arrested and brutalized, Rayo's psychological state deteriorates, revealing the collective trauma of a society under duress. He begins to experience hallucinations, perceiving another version of himself who is mad, while questioning the reality of Kayo's existence.

Bandle-Thomas encapsulates this existential crisis through Rayo's surreal dreams, which mirror the dystopian reality of a nation plagued by corruption and misrule. These dreams, as Bandle-Thomas illustrates, are images of a dystopian society as a result of bad leadership, corruption, and misgovernance. Misgovernance and bad leadership serve as precursors to psychosis, both on an individual and societal level. The anti-human policies of many African leaders can best be described as the actions of individuals who have lost touch with reality. One cannot help but wonder why a reasonable government would implement policies that are detrimental to the collective well-being of its citizens while remaining indifferent to their suffering, even in the face of widespread poverty and evident distress. Such governance represents a disconnect from the lived realities of the people, suggesting a deeper psychological detachment or even a form of collective delusion where leaders rationalize oppression and economic hardship as necessary or inevitable.

One germane issue the author condemns, which often leads to the societal breakdown of law and order, is the inability or lack of parental synergy in the upbringing of children, commonly referred to as "single parenthood." Rayo's vulnerability and reckless heroism are a consequence of poor parental care, particularly the absence of fatherly guidance. At the age of eight, he is left to grapple with the trauma of a father who abandons the family without leaving any trace of his whereabouts. Rayo explains that: "By the time I was eight, father was long gone. He simply packed his bag one morning and told mother, I was listening under the sheet, 'I'm sick of hearing your voice every day of my life'" (5). The burden of raising a hyperactive child such as Rayo falls solely on the mother. This is evidence of leadership failure within the home, which, in turn, impacts the wider society. Many street urchins, robbers, thugs and drug addicts are products of broken homes. A common trend these days is the rise of teenagers who have turned to the streets, abusing substances such as tramadol, codeine, kolos, Indian hemp, and drinking themselves into a stupor, thereby becoming a threat to society. In their drug-induced hallucinations, they perceive the world from a distorted perspective. Therefore, Rayo's eccentric behaviour can be traced to familial depression, and in an attempt to cope with it, he turns to drug use. According to Kayo, even Rayo's mother does not fully understand her son.

She couldn't understand why he chooses to drop out of a university scholarship for political reasons. He scarcely had any friends—all his friends had long given him up for a lunatic ... he had always been a loony, always lived in a dream world. He created lies and lived in a delirium of floating ghosts and pissed-out prophets. (19)

This hallucinatory existence, exacerbated by societal pressures, positions Rayo as a metaphor for Nigeria's schizophrenic state, a country oscillating between hope and despair, potential and ruin.

The prevalence of drug abuse among Nigerian youths, as depicted in Rayo's life, is an indication of personal despair and systemic neglect. Rayo is an unusual individual who, under the influence of drugs, exhibits eccentric behaviour. This results in him having bizarre dreams and telling strange stories. The effects of the drugs ultimately cause him to drop out of university and venture into politics. Satirically, many politicians in Africa, who are irrationally steering the affairs of the continent, are school dropouts. By implication, they are products of hard substances that keep them in a constant state of intoxication, causing them to behave unconsciously and act like madmen. Imagine a former governor in one of the states in Nigeria who thrived on social media propaganda, claiming to have revolutionized the education system under the initiative christened *EdoBEST*. The same government, however, shut down virtually all tertiary institutions, while the few that remained were starved of funds and subjected to draconian policies that nearly rendered them moribund. These actions are tantamount to those of someone suffering from dementia.

While unconscious on his bed, Kayo searches his brother's room and discovers unsettling items, including ashtrays filled with cigarette stubs. This scene shows a general societal issue, substance abuse and its link to mental health struggles. After consuming hard drugs, Rayo's unconscious state is vividly described: "thick sponge saliva dribbled from the side of his mouth" (28). He regains consciousness only through the intervention of Dr. Dakwa, who had previously acknowledged Rayo's intelligence. Now faced with Rayo's deteriorated state, the doctor expresses his shock: "He was such a sharp kid, really alive. I thought he was destined for greatness. What happened?" (30). This raises a crucial question: how many promising young ones whose futures have been derailed due to frustration stemming from bad leadership and flawed government policies? In Nigeria today, many youths turn to cybercrime (*yahoo yahoo*) and ritual practices as a desperate response to systemic failures. The lack of job opportunities and an enabling environment for businesses to thrive have heightened economic hardship, pushing many into mental distress. The rising frustration in the country has led to an increasing number of young people losing their grip on reality, wandering the streets in a state of psychological turmoil.

Bande-Thomas also introduces the story of a young law student who, after failing his law examinations four times, experiences a mental breakdown. While at home for the Christmas holiday, he suddenly loses touch with reality. He is later seen wandering the streets of Makurdi, dressed in a tattered wig and gown, frantically gesturing to passers-by and exclaiming, "Objection, my lord!" (96). His condition highlights the psychological toll of academic

pressure and personal failure, emphasizing the fragile nature of mental health when individuals lack adequate emotional, societal support and the lack of guidance and counselling.

Similarly, the story of Salihu reflects another case of societal vulnerability. Born in dire circumstances to a mother who was a beggar at a railway station, Salihu's life is shaped by hardship from the start. Growing up on the streets, he becomes a pickpocket and eventually recruits other boys into the same trade. His influence extends beyond petty crime, as he forms alliances with corrupt police officers who help secure the release of any of his boys caught in the act. The young boys who work under Salihu, terrorizing the railway station, are not merely criminals but victims of social neglect and economic despair. Their circumstances illustrate how societal depression and systemic failures contribute to mental health struggles, pushing many into cycles of crime and psychological instability.

The author vividly portrays the devastating impact of poverty on individuals and society. Tere, Rayo's girlfriend, is forced into prostitution due to extreme financial hardship. Desperate to fund her university education and purchase textbooks, she engages in relationships with multiple men, some old enough to be her grandfather. As an undergraduate at the University of Benin, Tere also bears the financial burden of supporting her three younger siblings, who are still in school. Her father, an engine driver for the Railway Corporation, earns a meagre salary, which he mostly spends on alcohol, leaving his family in dire financial distress. Tere's experience in prostitution is neither desirable nor fulfilling, yet she sees it as the only means of survival. Her story highlights the fact that poverty causes disillusionment and mental breakdown occasioned by endless struggles and societal neglect. The psychological impact of economic hardship forces many young women into exploitative and degrading situations, leading to long-term emotional and mental distress. Through Tere's plight, the author satirizes the issue of systemic poverty and its devastating consequences on individuals' mental well-being and moral choices. According to her:

I need my sugar daddies. I give them my body once in a while, and they keep my bank account comfortably in the black. It's a two-way street, I know. I offer them promises of rejuvenation—I make them young again for a fee. But they too—they take away something from me—my youth ... it's a two-way traffic.(25)

This is the harsh reality faced by many undergraduates and others who resort to prostitution for survival. Despite the degrading and immoral nature of this trade, Tere considers herself fortunate to have regular clients who patronize her. She explains that some of her course mates, who are not as lucky, travel to five-star hotels in Lagos in search of customers but often return empty-handed. Meanwhile, politicians continue to squander public funds on trivial matters, further widening the gap between the privileged and the impoverished. For Rayo, this stark inequality fuels deep frustration and resentment among the poor. His disillusionment is shown when he laments: "I walk on the streets and see the faces, the anger. And then in the papers, you read about those politicians in military uniform going to Milan to have a toothache examined. And I say to myself, is it worth it? Is it fucking worth it?" (26). To Tere and Rayo, prostitution becomes a desperate survival strategy. "It's called the end justifies the means" (113). However, this pursuit of financial stability comes at a heavy psychological and

emotional cost. The mental strain of engaging in such a lifestyle, coupled with the societal stigma and potential health risks, shows the tragic consequences of systemic poverty and government negligence.

Tere, in her vulnerable state, has experienced numerous disappointments stemming from her manipulative behaviour and her false persona toward men. She has undergone several abortions, each one a desperate attempt to cope with the consequences of her actions. Unfortunately, her story ends tragically, as she dies during an abortion, one that was a result of her illicit relationship with Alhaji, a wealthy older man who insisted she bears his child. However, Tere is not ready for motherhood; she seeks money, not the burden of a child. Before this tragic incident, Tere reflects on the hardship of her life and the poverty-stricken family she comes from, expressing deep frustration with the circumstances that have led her to this point. She says:

I feel like I'm living a lie. Life is tough, Kayo, it's bloody unfair. I feel like shouting at God. If he is there... it's not my fault that my family is poor. You can't hold that against me. And I wasn't the one who killed Jesus Christ. Why must you hold everything against me?... I am pregnant again, Kayo. (189-190)

This passage highlights Tere's disillusionment with life, where she feels trapped in a cycle of poverty and poor choices. Her mental and emotional turmoil validates societal challenges where government's neglect and harsh living conditions push individuals into compromising their values for survival.

Other web of stories in the novel draws attention to various issues of mental health resulting from disillusionment. The tragic story of Tijanni, a university undergraduate who comes to beg for food at Pategi's canteen, stands out as a glaring example of the mental strain and disillusionment caused by extreme poverty. Tijanni confesses that he has gone days without food, an experience that highlights the deep emotional and psychological effect of hunger and deprivation. Pategi, a kind-hearted man, offers him food, but Tijanni's distress speaks to the overwhelming weight of living in such dire circumstances.

Similarly, the story of Mr. Kazim, a staff member in one of the ministries on Lagos Island, illustrates the harsh realities of a low-income existence. Despite his hard work, Mr. Kazim earns a meagre salary of two hundred and fifty naira, which is insufficient to cover his basic needs, let alone secure a decent accommodation. Kazim's mental exhaustion and frustration are compounded by his constant struggle to meet his family's needs. He also works as a guard during weekends at a nearby factory, attempting to make ends meet, all the while enduring the indignity of living in a one-room apartment with his wife and two children, with a third on the way. Even his modest aspiration to buy a television for his family remains out of reach, as the price continually increases whenever he manages to save enough money.

To worsen these economic pressures, Kazim faces personal betrayal. His wife, who also sells sweets to help the family, is exploited by other men, particularly when she visits neighbours to watch television. When Kazim eventually discovers the affair, his emotional and psychological imbalance culminates in an act of violence, ripping off the penis of the man involved. This extreme reaction can be seen as a manifestation of the deep frustration, helplessness and

disillusionment that come from years of living in poverty, with no escape from the cycle of hardship. Kazim's mental health is severely impacted, as the pressures of poverty, betrayal and societal neglect push him to a breaking point.

Critical of the ugly political scenario in Africa, particularly in Nigeria, the author uses different stories to ridicule bad governance, whether civilian or military. Rayo, in his usual humorous disposition during class, which he dubs the "political science hour," decides to mock the political campaigns built on empty promises in Nigeria. He narrates the story of a politician who, during a pre-election campaign, promises the people numerous developments, such as a modern airport, a bridge and a well-equipped library in the school. Upon being questioned about building a bridge where there is no river in the community, the politician responds that they would create one. These are the types of visionless and psychotic politicians who parade themselves with vacuous promises.

Such politicians are notorious for hiring thugs and paying crowds for their campaigns. These actions are pointers to political deception and a detachment from reality, akin to the symptoms of psychosis. Further illustrating the fraudulent nature of Nigerian politics, Rayo shares a joke about a Nigerian president who finds himself in a sinking boat with the presidents of America and the Soviet Union. The three men agree to vote on who should be thrown overboard. While the American and Russian presidents each receive one vote, the Nigerian president announces that he has ten votes, shouting, "Long live democracy!" (34). This portrays the type of manipulated democracy practiced in Nigeria, where figures are rigged and elections are fraudulent. A notable example of this is the 2018 primary election for a presidential candidate of one of the major political parties, where the results reported triple the number of delegates who actually attended the primaries. The manipulation of such scenarios and the lack of connection to reality are key markers of psychotic behaviour in the political arena and the author uses these portrayals to criticize the state of governance in Nigeria.

Bandle-Thomas also ridicules the military administration of one of Nigeria's military dictators, using the story of Babagee and Mamagee in the fictional Zowabia nation as a clear case of military dictatorship and abuse of power. The president, Babagee, is portrayed as power-drunk, ruling with an iron fist and instilling fear within the population. He is depicted as having most of his savings in a Swiss bank, and in collaboration with the first lady, ensures that anyone who speaks out against the government is executed by soldiers.

Babagee's desire to kill Kukar Kurchia, a lawyer, is an indication of his deep-seated hatred for truth and dissent. The author uses this novel to lampoon the military administration of Babangida and the infamous killing of Dele Giwa. In the novel, Kukar Kurchia is eventually killed via a letter bomb, an action recommended by military commanders to avoid attracting international attention. This mirrors the real-life horrors of the Babangida and Abacha administrations, where arbitrary killings and gross violations of human rights were rampant.

Again, the stillbirth of Mamagee, the first lady, provides a psychological twist to the narrative. The president is holding a national conference to discuss how to deal with perceived enemies of his administration when he got the shocking news. The stillbirth becomes a metaphoric "abortion" of Babagee's ambition to become a field marshal, symbolizing the collapse of his desires and the futility of his authoritarian regime. Babagee attributes the stillbirth to his wife's

phobia of Kurchia Kukar, highlighting the psychological and emotional burdens carried by those in power. This scenario critiques the deep psychological trauma and paranoia that often accompany authoritarian rule, suggesting that the fear of dissent and the abuse of power can lead to severe mental health issues, both personal and societal. Honestly speaking, those who are ruthless with power are mentally unstable; they are either suffering from psychosis or other forms of mental health issues. Through these allegorical portrayals, Bandele-Thomas exposes the mental strain and psychological disintegration that often accompany dictatorial regimes, using the stillbirth and the president's irrational fears as metaphors for the instability and the neurosis of those in power.

Bandele-Thomas's critique of bribery and corruption within the judiciary and police force highlights not only the moral decay of governance but also raises questions about the mental stability of those who perpetuate such injustices. The author portrays a system where judges and police officers in Zowabia accept bribes to pervert justice, suggesting that individuals who engage in such acts may be psychologically compromised. For instance, during a court session, a man accused of murder boldly declares his innocence, publicly revealing that he had bribed a police officer with ten thousand American dollars. Rather than reprimanding the man, the judge apologizes to him, blaming the police officer for misrepresenting the bribe amount as ten thousand Zowabian dollars instead. The judge then declares thus:

... the case against you is dismissed. You're discharged and acquitted of all the charges preferred against you. You have ably demonstrated to this honourable court that you are a responsible citizen and a law abiding member of the community. It is totally inconceivable to this court that a man of your standing could have been responsible for cold-blooded multiple murders for which you are now standing in this courtroom. Accept my deepest apologies. You're a free man. (149)

This absurd exchange depicts the irrationality and moral bankruptcy of those in power, implying a form of mental instability. The judge's failure to uphold justice and his willingness to excuse corruption indicate a distorted sense of morality and rationality, traits often associated with psychological dysfunction. Bandele-Thomas uses this scenario to satirize not only the systemic corruption within governance but also to suggest that those who pervert justice may themselves be mentally unstable. By exposing the irrationality and ethical decay of such individuals, the author draws a connection between corrupt practices and psychological imbalance, emphasizing how the erosion of moral integrity can manifest as a form of collective mental illness within society. This portrayal serves as a stark reminder of the devastating impact of corruption on both governance and the mental well-being of those who perpetuate it. The Nigerian Police collects bribe as low as fifty kobo from commuters and drivers. The author sarcastically says that Nigeria is considering institutionalizing bribe taking by the police:

...Nigeria. They can boost-even as I speak of the most disciplined police force on the continent. Their police force has proved so profitable that their government is already contemplating turning it into a limited liability company, to be known as the "Bribe Etcetera" group of companies limited. (151)

Bandele-Thomas also showcases the portrayal of sycophancy in government and the decay of public infrastructure in the novel as satirical metaphors of the mental health crisis and widespread disillusionment caused by bad governance. The character of Professor Olentelaafaa, the presidential spokesman, exemplifies the psychological strain of sycophancy and moral compromise. Olentelaafaa engages in blatant lies and hypocrisy, sacrificing his integrity as an academic to curry favour with politicians in hopes of being appointed Vice Chancellor. His actions reveal a serious mental instability, as he abandons his principles and perpetuates a culture of deceit. This behaviour is emblematic of the psychological damage inflicted by a system that rewards corruption and sycophancy over merit and honesty, leaving individuals disillusioned and morally bankrupt.

The author further highlights the mental health implications of derelict infrastructure, particularly in the health sector. The general hospital where Rayo is circumcised is depicted as a chaotic and dysfunctional environment, with exorbitant costs for basic services and a severe shortage of personnel. The hospital environment is described as follows:

The queues, especially in the injection rooms, often stretched out across the length of the hospital itself. The overworked nurse and attendants were sometimes so ill-disposed, so foul-tempered that mere confrontation with them often effected instant cures in patients, without the benefit of medication. (10)

This paints a grim picture of a system in collapse. The exhaustion and frustration of healthcare workers lead to frequent misdiagnoses, including wrong prescriptions that result in patient deaths. The hospital's reliance on a single doctor, Dakwa, and the presence of quack doctors further endanger lives, as seen in the case of the OAU medical school dropout who botches Tere's abortion, ultimately leading to her death. The inability to access quality healthcare intensifies the mental strain on the populace, leaving many in a state of chronic anxiety and despair. These conditions not only endanger physical health but also worsen mental health struggles, as individuals are forced to navigate a system that fails to provide basic care and dignity. The decay extends to the education sector, where St. Peter's School is neglected. The school's outdated bucket system for waste disposal and deteriorating infrastructure contribute to the poor health of Baba Ayafa, the night soil man, whose plight becomes a rallying point for Rayo's protests. The pervasive state of decay in public institutions fuels anger, cynicism and disillusionment among the populace.

Conclusion

Bandele-Thomas uses scatological imagery, depictions of human waste and filth, to metaphorically represent the moral and psychological rot caused by bad leadership. These images evoke a sense of despair and depression to mirror the mental toll of living in a society where basic needs are unmet and systemic failures are the norm. Through these portrayals, Bandele-Thomas illustrates how bad governance not only undermines physical infrastructure but also inflicts profound psychological harm on individuals and communities. The pervasive disillusionment, anger and cynicism depicted in the novel are direct consequences of a system that prioritizes corruption and self-interest over the well-being of its citizens. Through the portrayal of mental health crisis fuelled by societal decay, the author calls for urgent reforms to address both the material and psychological needs of a nation in distress. The novel serves

as a satirical depiction of psychosis occasioned by bad governance, bad leadership, decayed infrastructure and systemic failures that perpetuate suffering and disillusionment.

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